

JUXTAPOSING BANGLADESH TO "MEIJI JAPAN" : A STUDY ON INITIAL CONDITIONS FOR DEVELOPMENT

M. Aslam Alam *

(**Abstract:** Japan is the economic superpower in the present day world with the most developed economy and society. The pre-war economic development starting from 'Meiji Restoration' was the most contributing factor to the post-war development. On the other hand, Bangladesh is one of the Least Developed Countries in the world. Macroeconomic and social development indicators suggest that Bangladesh has yet to go a long way to achieve economic emancipation. In this paper, an attempt has been made to juxtapose 'Independent Bangladesh' (1972) to 'Meiji Japan' (1868) in order to ascertain the factors contributing to Japanese development and Bangladeshi underdevelopment. In this paper 'Meiji Japan' refers to Japan at the time of 'Meiji Restoration'. During the Tokugawa era (1600 A. D. to 1860 A. D.), the emperors in Kyoto were the titular rulers of Japan, while the Tokugawa Shoguns at Edo (Tokyo) were the real rulers. In January 1868, the last Tokugawa Shogun was stripped of his powers and the administration was formally handed over to the Emperor Meiji. This event is known as 'Meiji Restoration' which marked the beginning of the Meiji era. During this era, the national slogan of Japan became *fokoku Kyohei* (enrich the country, strengthen the army). The 'Meiji Restoration' in 1868 brought the fundamental political and institutional changes which paved the way for Japan's rapid economic development. However, the present study concludes that the initial conditions in 'Meiji Japan' were more conducive to rapid modernization and economic growth than 'Independent Bangladesh'. This paper argues that the preparedness for rapid development in 'Meiji Japan' was a legacy of Tokugawa era and the unpreparedness for development in 'Independent Bangladesh' was also a legacy of the past.)

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Introduction

Japan is the economic superpower in the present day world with the most developed economy and society. Japan is the first country outside the western world to achieve such a feat. The miraculous development in the post-war period attracted innumerable studies on the dynamics of Japanese economic growth. It was not at all a difficult task to identify the pre-war economic development starting from Meiji Restoration as the most contributing factor to the post-war development. However, it will be incorrect to assume that Japan jumped from a backward feudal economy to a modern one. There is a consensus among the economic historians that Japanese development is a continuous process starting from the Tokugawa era.

On the other hand, Bangladesh is one of the Least Developed Countries in the world. Macro-economic and social development indicators suggest that Bangladesh has yet to go a long way to achieve economic emancipation. In this paper, an attempt will be made to juxtapose 'Independent Bangladesh' to 'Meiji Japan' in order to ascertain the factors contributing to Japanese development and Bangladeshi underdevelopment. We believe that "History surely does not repeat itself,.....[however]..... there exist patterns, still not discerned, common to the transition to modern economic growth, irrespective of time and place." [1] The understanding of the process of development in Japan will be helpful to draw implications and teachings for the developing countries in general and Bangladesh in particular. In the present study, we will mainly focus on the initial conditions for development when the countries started their development efforts.

Periodization and Background

Japan

Japan started her development efforts, consciously and vigorously, after the Meiji Restoration in 1868. The Restoration resulted in so much changes in the economy and society that it is considered as a revolution. To ascertain the initial conditions for development, we will look at the

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outcome of the Tokugawa era (1603-1860). It may be recalled that Tokugawa Ieyasu unified the country and began to rule in 1603. Administratively, the country had been divided into 270 Hans under the rule of the *daimyos*. They administered a rigid caste system of four classes consisting of warrior (*samurai*), farmer, artisan and merchant. The country embarked on the *sakoku* (isolation) policy in 1639 closing the door for the Westerners except the Dutch merchants who could do business at Nagasaki under the control of the *Bakufu*. The centralized feudal structure, which appropriated more characteristics of bureaucacy, had been firmly established. [2] There had been a strict control over travel and trade as well as freedom of occupation and enterprise. It had been a rice based agrarian economy with primitive technology where 40% of produces of the peasants were appropriated. The structure of the economy and the society continued until the Meiji Restoration, which, according to Lockwood, is a result of the release of long pent-up forces. Economic pressure induced class struggle, both inter and intra class, mercantile (*chonin*) influence, famines and natural disasters as well as intellectual renaissance and the Western gunboats and traders contributed largely to the emergence of the Meiji Revolution. [3]

Bangladesh

Unlike Japan, analyzing historical Bangladesh is a complex matter. It is not only because that the country, throughout her history, was entangled into regional and international politics but also for the changing structure of the society. Until the mid-nineteenth century, Japan had been insulated by the Pacific Ocean and the Sea of Japan against the foreign invaders. Bangladesh did not have such immunity. At around the time of beginning of the Tokugawa era, Bangladesh (then Bengal) was incorporated into the Mughal Empire and Dhaka was founded as the capital of the province of Bengal. Ironically, around the same time, Emperor Jahangir greeted the first British Merchant Thomas Roe at his court. At the beginning of the eighteenth century, when the Mughal Empire became weak, Bengal became independent and incorporated nearby state of Bihar and Orissa into it. With the death of Nawab Ali Bordi Khan, Bengal became weak due to

internal power struggle and conspiracy among the nobles. Consequently, Nawab Siraj-Ud-Doula lost the 'Battle of Palassy' in 1757 to the British who took over the control of the country with the assistance of the conspirators. The Permanent Settlement Arrangement of 1793, introduced by the British, implanted a far-reaching effect, which is yet to overcome, on the economy and society of Bangladesh. During their reign, the British, in pursuit of their colonial policy of divide and rule, successfully divided the community of Bengal into Muslims and Hindus. Accordingly, when they left India in 1947, Bengal was divided into agrarian east and industrialized west dominated by the Muslims and the Hindus respectively. In 1947, the East Bengal emerged as the eastern wing of Pakistan. But soon people realized that the West Pakistanis had internally colonized them. After a devastating war of liberation, Bangladesh emerged independent in December 1971. Development efforts for the people, of the people and by the people of Bangladesh have been undertaken since 1972. In our efforts to examine the initial conditions for development, we will look not only into the Pakistani days but also into British days because many of the shortcomings have their roots into those days.

Initial Conditions for Development

Homogeneity of people

'Meiji Japan' inherited the foundation works necessary for making a single community, namely, the standardization of language, the acceptance of similar ways of thinking and acting by the people of various provinces and the consequent similarity in social rules and customs and so forth. It was an outcome of 220 years seclusion. [4] Another striking similarity exists in the attitude towards and practice of religion. It had been achieved due to firm actions taken by different rules in different time. The massacre of 20,000 Buddhists by Nobunaga Oda (1533-82) in the Ikko Sect. Uprising, the crucifixion of the Christians at Nagasaki by Hideyoshi Toyotomi (1536-98), and the prohibition of the Christianity in 1635 and massacre of rebel Christians at Shimabara in 1638 by Shogun Iemitsu have largely contributed to this achievement.

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Bangladesh also enjoys this homogeneity of people. About 99% of the population are ethnic Bengali, about 85% of them are Muslims. [5] The division of Bengal in 1947 along the religious line and widespread communal rioting immediately preceding the division, forced many Hindu Bengalis from East Bengal to migrate to West Bengal in India. The non-Bengali Muslim immigrants from India also left the country in 1971. Consequently, Bangladeshis have become homogeneous people speaking the same language and sharing almost the same religion and culture.

Population growth

'Meiji Japan' inherited a stable population. Although population increased sharply during the early decades of Tokugawa era, it was standing still during the final one and one-half centuries before the 1860s. The practice of population control was wide spread during the period. It reflects the Japanese preference of higher standard of living and rate of savings. [6]

On the other hand, the Bangladesh population has been sharply increasing since the last half of the Nineteenth century. The long-term growth of population has been 2.6% per annum since the 1950s. [7] Broomfield observes that Muslim population in East Bengal was growing twice as fast as the Hindus by 10%. He attributed the reasons to the fertile land of East Bengal. [8] Consequently, Bangladesh has inherited a high population growth.

Education

Meiji Japan inherited a highly educated population. It was true for both the elite and the commoners. Dore estimates that, at the time of Restoration, 40 to 50% of all Japanese boys and perhaps 15% of girls were getting some formal schooling outside their homes, and singles out important Tokogawa legacies as attitudes to popular education, training in abstract analysis, ... the development of a respect for merit ...and the strengthening of a collective ideology. [9] The samurai elite used to get education at Shogunal and Domain level schools as well as the private

academies (*shijuku*) whereas the commoners were educated in *terakoya* where reading writing and abacus were taught.

On the other hand, the low level of literacy in Bangladesh is perhaps one of the foremost impediment to development. In 1974, the adult literacy rate was only 25.8% (male 37.2% and female 13.2%). [10] The adult male literacy was 10% in 1901, and out of the educated male, only 6.8% were Muslims. [11] It was mainly due to the discriminatory policy, which was pursued for one and a half centuries, of the British against the Muslims. The upper caste Hindus of Bengal monopolized the education. "Places in schools, especially in primary schools, which were mostly private, were difficult to obtain, for provision had been made for the elite, not the masses ... [Even] not every *bhadralok* (elite) family could afford the education it desired for all its son." [12] The situation started to change in the early 20th century when the British changed their attitude towards the Muslims, obviously for political reasons. It is a irony that number of primary schools in East Pakistan dropped from 29,663 in 1947. 48 to 28,308 in 1968-69 despite a huge population growth, were as it registered four and a half times increase during the same period in West Pakistan. [13] Consequently, the government of independent Bangladesh had to face an uphill task of educating a huge population.

Urbanization

The existence of a high rate of urbanization in Tokugawa Japan is another striking feature, which helped developing the market economy from the very beginning. In 1868, Edo (Tokyo) was as large as London with more than one million population. The population of Osaka, Kyoto, Nagoya and Kanazawa were 300,000, 200,000, 100,000 and 100,000 respectively. Besides the big cities, towns and urban communities had been established in many places like Hiroshima, Nagasaki, Sendai, Wakayama, Kagoshima and Sakai. [14]

At the beginning of the century, "in Bengal and the provinces tributary to it, there was one great city, a few towns and innumerable villages." [15] The great city was Calcutta with a population more than one million. In 1947, it was awarded to India. Dhaka and Chittagong were two other towns with more than 35,000 population. At that time, only .03 per cent people lived at the urban centers. Interestingly, 60% of the urban population

comprised of the Hindus, majority of whom left East Bengal subsequently. [16] In 1970, the urban population constituted only 7.6 per cent of the total population [17] with Dhaka, Chittagong, Rajshahi and Khulna as major cities and about 17 district towns including Comilla, Sylhet, Rangpur and Barisal. Small towns numbering about 50 also existed. Since then, the urban population has been growing at a rate of more than 6 per cent per annum. [18] However, Bangladesh remains as a pre-dominantly rural country.

Agriculture

'Meiji Japan' inherited an agriculture, which employed as much as 72% of the total labor force; almost without anymore uncultivated arable land, and organized by small holding, fragmented peasants. [19] The peasants were tied to the land by the social caste system and they could retain 35.43% of the produces. One of the significant developments of Tokugawa era was commercialization of the agriculture. "By the 1860s the degree of commercialization ... for the country as a whole ... was probably about 60 per cent." [20] The other significant development was very high level of productivity mainly contributed by irrigation, improved seeds, and better methods of planting, weeding, and use of fertilizer.

Bangladesh agriculture has some similarities with Japanese agriculture in the sense that it also employs about 75% of the labour force. No more uncultivated arable land is available, and small holding and fragmented peasants do farming. However, there are some differences. Firstly, the agricultural growth rate has been unable to keep up with the population growth rate. Secondly, about 50% of the peasants are land less and a majority of the others are marginal farmers. Thirdly, it is characterized by share cropping where the peasants have to bear the cost of inputs and could retain 50% of the produces. Fourthly, the peasants had been permanently indebted to the moneylenders and forced to sale the produces to them in advance at very low prices. Fifthly, the surplus generated by agriculture during the British period had been invested in Calcutta, which later became part of India, and the surplus during the Pakistan period had been utilized for industrial development of West Pakistan. Sixthly, it was characterized by secular decline in productivity.

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Manufacturing

Tokugawa Japan made considerable advance in the manufacturing sector also. Much of the industrial units were engaged in sake brewing, bleaching, salt, soy sauce, oil pressing etc. The diaspora of processes and techniques, from urban to rural areas, due to relatively higher urban labor and raw material costs and guild restrictions, have been documented by many researchers. [21] All these provided the foundation for later industrialization.

Bengal had been rich in rural industries until the taking over by the British, which destroyed all the manufacturing capabilities in order to make it a market for British products. During the last decades of the British rule, taking the opportunity of the liberal policies, industrialization did take place in Bengal but almost exclusively in Calcutta. In 1948, the contribution of manufacturing sector to the GDP of Pakistan was one per cent only. [22] Until 1961, it grew at an annual rate of 15% with concentration of industries in West Pakistan, but the cost of industrialization was largely borne by East Pakistan as its jute earned more than 60% of the foreign exchange and its agriculture was subjected to net transfer of resources to the import and import substituting sectors. [23] Consequently, the share of manufacturing sector in GDP was only 8.3% in 1972-73. [24] More importantly, at the time of independence, Bangladesh lacked industrial entrepreneurs and skilled labour force. To make the situation worse, the existing labour force had been turned into a radical group due to politicization during the struggle for liberation.

Commerce and finance

Tokugawa era achieved significant progress in commerce and finance. The existence of big cities and about 2000 castle towns, quite developed road network and transportation system, the need for selling of rice by the *dimyos* and increasing agricultural productivity have largely contributed to this progress. The coins-gold, silver and copper-used to be minted by the *Bakufu*, but the *Hans* were allowed to issue convertible paper money. This system contributed to the development of the financial sector. Private

exchange houses played the role of the modern banks. Because of the importance of the sector, merchants enhanced their position in the society and many members of *Samurai* also engaged in this sector. Thus, formulation of commercial capital was greatly facilitated during the period and later contributed to the industrialization process. [25]

During the first century of British rule, commerce and finance in Bengal was completely controlled by the British, especially in the urban centers. Later, the non-Bengalis from North India took over a substantial share. In the rural areas in East Bengal, it was dominated by the moneylenders and merchants who were mostly Hindu. No portion of the accumulated capital was invested in East Bengal. During Pakistan era, this sector registered a significant growth under the control of West Pakistanis and immigrant non-Bengalis who left the country in 1971. The system largely contributed to the transfer of financial resources to West Pakistan. Quite understandably, immediately after the independence, the government took over the control of all the financial institutions and a big chunk of the export and import business.

Social and political forces

We have mentioned before that the centralized feudal structure has been firmly established during the Tokugawa era. The society was divided into four classes with the *Samurai* at the top and the merchants at the bottom. The *Samurai* were all powerful, but not necessarily rich. However they were well educated. We have discussed before that education has been much emphasized during the Tokugawa era. By the end of the era, there were about 27 *shogunal* schools teaching medicine, weapons, western languages, and Confucianism. All the domains have their own schools to educate the *Samurai*. The principal objective of these schools was to implant leadership quality and high standard of moral, mainly by teaching Confucianism, among the children of the elite. [26] Mecpherson argues that "the promotion of Japanese style Confucianism ... bred mental attitudes ready to assimilate western science and technology and trained a large body of *Samurai* in the bureaucratic and organizing skills and the

discipline which were invaluable for running the Meiji government and the modern army and the factories. [27] The societal structure also promoted 'group oriented' and 'community centered' attitudes among the elite and the commoners as well. Minami rightly opines that the capable leaders and entrepreneurs were a further legacy from the Tokugawa period. Furthermore, the Meiji Revolution was a revolution from within. The commoners did not take part in the process any way other than obeying the authority. Immediately before the Revolution, the feudal Japan had been showing all the signs of the capitalistic mode of production. For these reasons, the Meiji government could easily introduce the state-led market economy in Japan.

There exists a sharp contrast between Japan and Bangladesh in this regard. Due to the land policy of the British, a semi-feudal structure had been established in the Bengal society. It was divided into five classes with hierarchical position of landlords, semi-landlords, moneylenders, rich farmers, and peasants, artisans and craftsmen. For more than one and a half centuries, the top three classes exclusively controlled the society. These classes comprised of the upper cast Hindus. The Muslims and the lower caste Hindus were in the last three classes. The members of the top classes were parasite in nature. They extracted their income by squeezing the peasantry who did not have any land owning rights and spend the surplus in Calcutta consuming imported luxury goods. Due to the change in the government policy at the end of the nineteenth century, muslim rich farmers got the land woning right. Thenceforward, they started their struggle for socio-political rights. By 1947, they became powerful enough to divide Bengal permanently. With the migration of top three classes, they emerged as the dominant class in East Pakistan. However, their struggle for authority continued, because the Civil Service, the Army, Commerce and Industry were dominated by the West Pakistanis. They emerged victorious in 1971 when Bangladesh came into being. But in the process, they became fragmented.

Unlike the Japanese education system, the education in Bengal was designed to produce clerks to serve the British, not to imbue leadership quality. The system remained basically unchanged during the Pakistani era.

For the last two and a half centuries before independence, the population of Bangladesh practically developed hatred against authority, because the positions of authority had always been occupied by either the British or the upper caste Hindu or the West Pakistanis, and they exercised their power in highly discriminatory and exploitative ways. It is noteworthy that, despite all the changes up to the independence, the semi-feudal structure of the society had remained unchanged; only the players had been changed. All these factors will play a crucial role in the later development efforts of Bangladesh. [28]

Conclusion

We have so far made a comparative study of initial conditions in the social and economic front in 'Meiji Japan' and 'Independent Bangladesh'. Following our discussion, we can put forward the following observations:

1. Both the countries had the common characteristic of homogeneity of people in terms of language, ethnicity, religion and culture. However, the homogeneity was rather a recent phenomenon in case of Bangladesh. Moreover, while Japan had been successful in complete integration of the minorities like the *Ainus* and the *Okinawans* as well as the religious minorities into the mainstream Japanese culture, in case of Bangladesh a small portion of religious and ethnic minorities continued to exist.
2. 'Meiji Japan' inherited a highly stable population, which did not grow significantly for almost one century. In contrast, 'Independent Bangladesh' inherited a population, which had been growing at more than two per cent per annum for the last one century.
3. 'Meiji Japan' inherited an educated population with male and female literacy of 43% and 15% respectively, whereas the rates of literacy for male and female were 37.2% and 13.2% respectively in 'Independent Bangladesh.'
4. Regarding urbanization, 'Independent Bangladesh' could be compared at par with 'Meiji Japan.'
5. Agriculture in 'Meiji Japan' had been far advanced than that of Bangladesh. The former was capable of producing sufficient food for

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5. Agriculture in 'Meiji Japan' had been far advanced than that of Bangladesh. The former was capable of producing sufficient food for

domestic consumption as well as cash crops for export, and generating surpluses, which were not possible for the Bangladesh agriculture.

6. Because of time-difference (1868 and 1972). 'Independent Bangladesh' was advanced, in terms of manufacturing capabilities and level of technology, than Japan. However, Japan was far advanced in terms of entrepreneurship, managerial capability and skilled labour, and capability to absorb new technology.
7. Considering the time-lag (1868 to 1972), Japan was more advanced than Bangladesh in indigenous commerce and finance.
8. The social and political forces in Japan were less fragmented, highly trained, motivated, far sighted, and ready to sacrifice personal or class interest in favour of national interest. But the situation in Bangladesh was different.

From the above discussion, we conclude that the initial conditions in 'Meiji Japan' were more conducive to rapid modernization and economic growth than 'Independent Bangladesh'. While it is true that the preparedness for development in Japan was a legacy of Tokugawa era, it is also true that the unpreparedness for development in Bangladesh was also a legacy of the past.

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28. For a detailed account on the issue, please see Kirsten Westergard, 1985, J. H. Broomfield, 1967, and S. K. Chakraborty, 1978.

Glossary of Japanese Words

Meiji Japan: Japan at the time of Meiji Restoration in 1868 A. D.

Tokugawa era: The era between 1600 A. D. to 1860 A. D.

Han: The Domains or fiefs of the quasi-independent lords.

Daimyo: Lord or ruler of a han.

Samurai: The warrior class in a rigid fourfold Confucian-type hierarchy.

Sakoku: The policy of isolation or closing the country.

Bakufu: The central government at Edo (Tokyo).

Chonin : Mercantile.

Shijuku: Elite private academies.

Sake: Japanese rice-wine.

Terakoya: Small schools for the commoners.

Ainu: The original inhabitants of the Northern territories of Japan.

Okinawan: The original inhabitants of Okinawa Island.